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Strategic Planning and Decision-Making in the Context of Educational Reform: Insights from Secondary School Leaders

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Abstract

This study explores the experiences and perspectives of secondary school leaders navigating strategic planning and decision-making in the context of educational reform in the Philippines. Using a hermeneutic phenomenological approach, semi-structured interviews were conducted with eight purposively selected participants. Thematic analysis revealed five key themes: navigating reform challenges, strategic decision-making for school improvement, educational synergy, the importance of stakeholder involvement, and the challenges faced in implementing strategic plans. The study advocates for a dynamic, inclusive strategic process and highlights the need for continuous professional development and data-driven decision-making. Implications for policy and practice include the integration of comprehensive strategic planning mechanisms in schools.

Keywords: *strategic planning, decision-making, educational reform, secondary school leaders, Philippines*

Introduction

Strategic planning is critical for educational leaders, particularly in the context of implementing reforms designed to improve school performance and student outcomes (Fullan, 1985). The K-12 curriculum in the Philippines, introduced to enhance the quality of basic education, has presented several challenges for school leaders responsible for implementing these changes (Republic Act No. 10533, 2013). This study aims to explore how secondary school leaders navigate strategic planning and decision-making within the context of these educational reforms.

Research Questions

The general objective of the study is to explore the lived experiences of secondary school leaders in implementing strategic plans during educational reform and to understand their perceptions regarding the impact of strategic planning on educational reforms in their schools. Specifically, the study aims to answer the following questions:

1. What are the lived experiences of secondary school leaders in implementing strategic plans during educational reform?
2. How do secondary school leaders perceive the impact of strategic planning on educational reforms in their schools?

Literature Review

Educational leadership has evolved significantly over time, with strategic planning becoming an essential tool for school improvement. Fullan's Change Process Theory (1985) emphasizes the role of leadership in navigating reforms, while Fiedler's Contingency Theory (1964) underscores the importance of aligning leadership styles with specific situational factors. Strategic decision-making is influenced by factors such as school culture, stakeholder involvement, and external pressures (Leithwood, Harris, & Hopkins, 2020). Prior studies highlight the need for school leaders to engage in collaborative decision-making, using data to inform strategies that address the diverse needs of their schools (VanGronigen, 2019).

Methodology

This study employed a hermeneutic phenomenological approach (van Manen, 1990), focusing on the lived experiences of secondary school leaders in Quezon City, Philippines. Eight principals with at least five years of experience participated in semi-structured interviews. Purposive sampling ensured that the participants were actively involved in strategic planning related to educational reform. Participants were selected based on their postgraduate qualifications or specialized training in educational leadership, proven experience in implementing educational reforms, recognition for innovative practices, and active involvement in community activities. These criteria ensured that participants had both theoretical knowledge and practical expertise to provide valuable insights. Data were analyzed using Braun and Clarke's (2006) thematic analysis, which involved coding, identifying themes, and interpreting findings within the context of the participants' experiences.

Results and Discussion

Five major themes emerged from the analysis:

Navigating Educational Reform Challenges: Participants reported facing significant challenges in aligning school practices with the requirements of the K-12 curriculum. They noted that changes in student demographics and resource limitations complicated the reform process. The implementation of intended projects or programs may be restricted by limited financial resources, requiring careful

planning in terms of allocation and prioritization.

“One of the factors, that I will consider, when making a decision, of course, you will see, if the budget is able... to provide the resources... Also, the facilities that we have in the school, that is also what needs to be...” (P 178, Roberto, L49-51)

Managing finances is one of the essential responsibilities of the school head. School fund must be managed properly for the benefit of the school (Aina & Bipath, 2020). Additionally, concurred that the absence of financial support in schools because of the criteria of school categorization prevented the achievement of good quality education needed by learners in the country.

“The bulk of the responsibility of a School Head are the students' performance. And at the same time, because our primary concern is the performance of the students.” (Maria, L 44-45)

Her statements reflected an in depth understanding of the critical role that academic success played in determining how students' lives progress. Maria's story emphasized how crucial it is for school administrators to create an environment that supports students' success.

Strategic Decision-Making for School Improvement: School leaders emphasized the importance of strategic decision-making in fostering school improvement. They highlighted the need for flexibility and innovation when developing plans to meet the diverse needs of students.

“We align all our plans. All the interventions, the SOB, the school budget operation, the annual implementation plan, all of those are aligned with the Matatag Agenda.” (P 170, Ana, L61-63)

The participants discussed the alignment of strategic plans with educational reform objectives, highlighting the importance of coherence and adherence to policies. Plans should be strategically stated and in line with the school's goal and vision, rather than only serving as checkboxes to complete external obligations (Carvalho et al., 2021).

“Allocating resources is another common problem faced by leaders, who have to strike a balance between the current budgetary constraints and the needs for staff training, textbooks, and updated technology. Leaders work with stakeholders to find alternative funding sources, carry out in-depth evaluations of the resources currently available, rank needs according to reform goals, and work together to secure support for budget reallocation.” (P 163, Sandro, L81-86)

It discussed the tangible resources like budgetary constraints, staff training, textbooks, and technology, emphasizing the importance of allocating these resources effectively to meet the needs of the school.

Educational Synergy and Collaboration: Collaborative efforts between teachers, parents, and administrators were seen as essential to successful strategic planning. Participants stressed the importance of involving all stakeholders in decision-making processes to ensure the sustainability of reforms.

“We involve our stakeholders here, like Barangay Captain, we have the PTA, the Government Council... Some others debate but reconcile at the end... We need to involve the stakeholders, especially our teachers.” (P 171, Lara, 67-69)

“Feedbacking... I start with the students... Then, when it comes to teachers... for the parents, the community, when we have a focus group discussion, that is where it comes out in the school governing council.” (P 123, Ana, L119-121)

Stakeholder Involvement: Ensuring effective participation from teachers, parents, and students was cited as a key factor in the success of strategic plans. Leaders noted that fostering a sense of ownership among stakeholders improved the implementation of reforms.

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Challenges in Implementing Strategic Plans: The participants reported that limited resources, insufficient professional development, and resistance from staff posed significant challenges. They advocated for ongoing professional development to equip teachers and staff with the skills needed for successful reform implementation.

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The findings of this study underscore the complexity of strategic planning in educational reform. School leaders are tasked with navigating multiple challenges, from resource constraints to stakeholder engagement, in their efforts to implement reforms effectively. The study supports Fullan's (1985) emphasis on leadership as a critical factor in educational change and highlights the need for ongoing professional development (Mahardhika & Raharja, 2023).

Conclusions

This study contributes to the understanding of strategic planning and decision-making in the context of educational reform. It highlights

the critical role of school leaders in navigating the complexities of reform implementation. It emphasizes the need for continuous collaboration and professional development to ensure the success of these efforts.

Students, parents, teachers, school administrators, and future researchers all play vital roles in the education planning process. Students should engage in school planning to ensure their needs are addressed, and schools should invest in teacher training. Parents need to advocate for equitable resource allocation and support long-term studies to understand the impact of reforms on their children's learning. Teachers should actively participate in strategic planning, utilize professional development, and promote standardized best practices. School administrators must involve all stakeholders in planning and exploring equitable funding models. Future researchers should focus on longitudinal studies, compare educational systems, and study emerging technologies to enhance strategic planning and reform efforts.

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